

Steric Enhancement of Resonance—Evidence from Kinetic Study on some Acetophenones[†]

M. KRISHNA PILLAY* and S. PALANIVELU

Department of Chemistry, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirappalli-620 028

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The kinetics of oxidation of some mono-, di- and tri-substituted acetophenones by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in 50% (v/v) methanol-water mixture at constant ionic strength and at 20, 30 and 40° have been studied spectrophotometrically and the rate constants determined by least-squares analysis. Electron-withdrawing groups in the ring facilitate the oxidation of the acetyl function while electron-releasing groups retard the rate. The rate constant values for the oxidation of 3-substituted-4-alkoxyacetophenones are computed based on the principle of additivity of group effects. The observed rate constants are significantly lower than the calculated values. This is attributed to the phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance (SER). 3,5-Disubstituted-4-methoxyacetophenones have higher observed rate constant values than the calculated ones. The steric inhibition of resonance (SIR) operates in these systems. In the case of 3-halogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones, the importance of SER increases with increase in the bulkiness of the 3-substituents. The difference between the calculated and observed multiple substituent constants of 3-substituted-4-methoxyacetophenones also leads support for SER.

THE concept of steric enhancement of resonance (SER) was put forward first by Ballah and Uma¹ during their study on electrical dipole moments of certain substituted anisoles and thioanisoles. Further studies provided evidence for the phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance²⁻²⁰. With a view to furnishing further evidence for the above phenomenon the kinetics of oxidation of suitably substituted acetophenones with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol at three temperatures, viz. 20, 30 and 40°, were carried out and the data analysed. This is in continuation of our earlier work⁸.

Experimental

The commercial samples of 2-methoxy-, 2,6-dimethoxy- and 2,5-dimethoxy-acetophenones (Bio-Organics, India) were used as such. 3-Methylacetophenone was prepared from *m*-tolunitrile using the Grignard reagent. 4-Methoxy-3-methyl- and 4-ethoxy-3-methyl-acetophenones were synthesised by the alkylation of 4-hydroxy-3-methylacetophenone, obtained by the acetylation of *o*-cresol followed by the Fries rearrangement. 4-Alkoxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenones were synthesised by the alkylation of 4-hydroxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone which was prepared by the acetylation of 2,6-dimethylphenol. The *meta*-halogenoacetophenones were prepared from *m*-aminoacetophenone by Sandmeyer reaction. The 3-halogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones were obtained by the diazotisation of *o*-anisidine and subsequent conversion into the *o*-halogenoanisole by

Sandmeyer reaction followed by acetylation. 3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxyacetophenone was prepared as per literature procedure. The corresponding bromo- and iodo-acetophenones were obtained by bromination and iodination of *p*-hydroxyacetophenone followed by methylation. The compounds were carefully purified till their physical constants agreed with the literature values. The purity of each compound was checked by analytical tlc just before the use for kinetic study.

Methanol (AnalaR) was distilled (b.p. 64.5°) and the middle-cut was collected and used. Sodium hydroxide (AnalaR) was used as such. Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (E. Merck, G.R.) was used without further purification. A 50% (v/v) methanol-water mixture (solvent) was prepared in double-distilled water. All the solutions were prepared using this solvent mixture. Potassium chloride (AnalaR) was used as such for maintaining constant ionic strength.

Kinetic procedure: The oxidation kinetics of the compounds under pseudo-first order condition were followed spectrophotometrically using a Carl-Zeiss uv-visible double beam spectrophotometer provided with thermostated cell holders, with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) as the oxidant in 50% (v/v) methanol-water mixture and with 0.25 *M* potassium chloride (A.R.) to maintain ionic strength. The concentrations of the solutions used were 10⁻³ - 10⁻⁵ *M*. Purified nitrogen was passed through the solutions to drive away any dissolved oxygen. The change in optical density in the absorption maximum of the oxidant (concn. 10⁻³ - 10⁻⁴ *M*) at 420 nm

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($\epsilon = 23.78 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was followed periodically. Solvent oxidation was checked and found to be negligible. The rate constants were calculated by least-squares analysis and the accuracy of the data was judged by their correlation coefficient (r) values. In most cases, $r = 0.999$.

Product analysis: A mixture of acetophenone (0.214 g) potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (2.481 g) in the molar ratio 1 : 4, sodium hydroxide (0.492 g) and potassium chloride (0.186 g) was taken in methanol-water mixture (50%, 40 ml) in a 100 ml flask and stirred at 30° for 12 h. The solvent was evaporated in a flash-evaporator. The resulting clear reddish solution was cooled, acidified and extracted with methylene dichloride (6 × 5 ml). The organic layer was washed with cold water, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered to remove the disiccant and evaporated in a water-bath. A creamy mass (0.145 g) obtained was identified to be benzoic acid by co-tlc with an authentic sample and by m.m.p. determination after purification by crystallisation from water.

Results and Discussion

The rates of oxidation of some mono-, di- and tri-substituted-acetophenones with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol have been determined and presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RATES OF OXIDATION OF SOME METHYL-, METHOXY- AND ETHOXY-ACETOPHENONES BY ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL

Substrate	$k_2 (\times 10 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		
	20°	30°	40°
Acetophenone	2.97	5.59	11.7
3-Methylacetophenone	2.28	4.06	8.31
4-Methoxyacetophenone	1.83	3.09	6.21
4-Methoxy-3-methylacetophenone	1.20	1.89	3.80
	(1.40)*	(2.24)	(4.41)
4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone	1.99	3.33	7.38
	(1.08)	(1.83)	(3.13)
4-Ethoxyacetophenone	2.36	4.45	8.16
4-Ethoxy-3-methylacetophenone	1.14	2.08	4.14
	(1.81)	(3.23)	(5.79)
4-Ethoxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone	2.70	3.88	4.62
	(1.89)	(2.86)	(4.11)

* Calculated values.

The second order rate constant (k_2) for the oxidation of acetophenone and 3-methylacetophenone at 30° are 5.59×10^{-1} and $4.06 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively. 4-Methoxyacetophenone reacts ($k_2 = 3.09 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) about two times slower than acetophenone. Electron donation from the substituent decreases the rate. The reaction rate is still lower, nearly three times for 4-methoxy-3-methylacetophenone ($k_2 = 1.89 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$). This decrease in the rate does not seem to be solely due to the 3-methyl group because the rate constant of 4-methoxy-3-methylacetophenone is 15% lower than the value predicted on the basis of the principle of additivity of substituent effects²¹, indicating

that there is greater electron-release by the 4-methoxy group to the reaction site, which is presumably due to a steric effect caused by the methyl group *ortho* to it. The *ortho*-methyl group forces the methoxy group to adopt a preferred orientation *trans* to it²². Thus the probability of the methoxy group becoming co-planar with the benzene ring increases as the alkoxy group can no longer rotate freely. Such a situation results in enhanced resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the aromatic ring. 4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone is oxidised with a reaction rate $3.33 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ while the predicted value is $1.63 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The observed value is not only higher than the calculated value but also higher than that of 4-methoxyacetophenone, indicating the predominance of the +I effect of the methoxy group over its -M effect. The conventional phenomenon of steric inhibition of resonance is found to operate in this compound. The effect of OC_2H_5 group on the rate of oxidation of the acetyl function has also been studied. 4-Ethoxyacetophenone has a rate constant of $4.45 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 30° (Table 1). The decrease in the rate constant from that of acetophenone is 1.14 unit. When compared with the decrease caused by OCH_3 group, *i.e.* 2.5 unit, this is smaller. This reveals that the OC_2H_5 group does not effectively conjugate with the acetyl function in the *para*-position as OCH_3 group does. The ethoxy group has a σ value of -0.25 whereas methoxy has a σ value²³ of -0.27. However, when a methyl group is present in the *ortho*-position its conjugation with the acetyl function increases very much as shown by the large decrease in the rate constant ($k_2 = 2.08 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) of 4-ethoxy-3-methylacetophenone. The observed rate constant is lower than the predicted value ($k_2 = 3.23 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) showing that steric enhancement of resonance operates to a larger extent in this compound than in the anisole derivative. The ethoxy group being bulkier than the methoxy group tries to remain most of the time in a position *trans* to the *ortho*-methyl group in order to avoid steric interaction with the methyl group. In this position it is able to conjugate effectively as the restriction to rotation is greater. This results in a greater decrease in the oxidation rate of the acetyl group. The rate constant for 4-ethoxy-3,5-dimethylacetophenone is $3.88 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. This value is higher than the calculated value ($k_2 = 2.35 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) due to steric inhibition of resonance.

The oxidation kinetics of some halogenoacetophenones have been studied and the data are collected in Table 2. 3-Fluoro-4-methoxyacetophenone has a rate constant of $6.28 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 30°. There is an increase in the rate constant. This may be due to the +I effect of the fluorine atom from the *meta*-position with respect to the acetyl group. 3-Fluoroacetophenone itself is oxidised at a faster rate ($k_2 = 12.5 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$). This may be the reason for the higher rate in the case of 3-fluoro-4-methoxyacetophenone. However, the

TABLE 2—RATES OF OXIDATION OF SOME FLUORO-, CHLORO-, BROMO-, IODO- AND METHOXY-ACETOPHENONES BY ALKALINE HEXA-CYANOFERRATE(III) IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL

Substrate	$k_2 (\times 10 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		
	20°	30°	40°
Acetophenone	2.97	5.59	11.7
3-Fluoroacetophenone	8.17	12.5	21.2
3-Chloroacetophenone	7.33	14.2	31.3
3-Bromoacetophenone	8.17	14.5	31.6
3-Iodoacetophenone	9.53	21.9	45.2
4-Methoxyacetophenone	1.83	3.09	6.21
3-Fluoro-4-methoxyacetophenone	3.47	6.23	11.7
	(5.03)*	(6.91)	(12.9)
3-Chloro-4-methoxyacetophenone	2.77	5.86	11.2
	(4.55)	(7.85)	(12.9)
3-Bromo-4-methoxyacetophenone	2.90	5.88	11.7
	(5.08)	(8.02)	(16.8)
3-Iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone	3.75	6.46	13.7
	(5.87)	(12.05)	(23.9)
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxyacetophenone	—	29.3	62.2
		(19.9)	(44.4)
3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxyacetophenone	—	31.1	69.0
		(20.8)	(45.8)
3,5-Diiodo-4-methoxyacetophenone	—	29.9	62.0
		(47.0)	(92.7)

* Calculated values.

calculated value is $6.91 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ which is higher than the observed one at 30°. There is a net decrease in the rate of oxidation by 10%. This may be accounted by the new effect. 3-Chloro-, 3-bromo- and 3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenones are oxidised at higher rates, viz. 5.66×10^{-1} , 5.88×10^{-1} and $6.46 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$, respectively. The observed rate constants of these compounds are also found to be lower than the calculated values (Table 2). This behaviour is in conformity with the SER. The steric inhibition of resonance is observed for 3,5-dichloro- and 3,5-dibromo-4-methoxyacetophenones whose observed rate constants are higher than the calculated values.

Effect of van der Waals radii on SER: The difference between the calculated and observed rate constants increases with increase in the size of the halogen atom. The k_2 values are furnished in Table 3 along with the van der Waals radii of the corresponding halogen atoms. The plot of Δk_2 (difference between $k_{2(\text{calcd})}$ and $k_{2(\text{obs})}$) versus the van der Waals radii of the halogen atoms is linear (Fig. 1). The importance of steric enhancement

 Fig. 1. van der Waals Radii vs Δk_2 .

of resonance increases with increase in the bulkiness of halogens.

Hammett relationship: The effect of substituents on the rate of oxidation of acetophenones has been analysed making use of Hammett relationship. The $\log k/k_0$ values are plotted against the corresponding σ values of the substituents. The substituents are so chosen that some are electron-repelling while others are electron-seeking. The slope of the straight line obtained by least-squares analysis gives the value of ρ ($r=0.960$). This reveals that the mono-substituted-acetophenones reasonably obey the Hammett equation in this reaction. A positive ρ value (+1.45) obtained in this case indicates that the reaction is facilitated by electron-withdrawing groups.

The effect of multiple substitution on the reactivity of side chain can be expressed by the Hammett equation in the form²⁴,

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \Sigma \sigma$$

where, k is the rate constant of disubstituted acetophenone and k_0 is that of acetophenone. When $\log k/k_0$ is divided by the reaction constant (ρ) determined as above, it gives the observed multiple

TABLE 3—CHANGE OF RATE CONSTANTS WITH CHANGE IN VAN DER WAALS RADII OF HALOGENS

Acetophenones	$k_2 (\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		van der Waals radii Å of 3-substituents	$k_{2(\text{calcd.})} - k_{2(\text{obs.})} (\Delta k_2)$
	Obs.	Calcd.		
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy-	0.628	0.691	1.85	0.068
3-Chloro-4-methoxy-	0.566	0.785	1.80	0.219
3-Bromo-4-methoxy-	0.588	0.802	1.95	0.214
3-Iodo-4-methoxy-	0.646	1.205	2.15	0.559

substitution constant ($\Sigma\sigma_{(obs.)}$). This value is then compared with the $\Sigma\sigma_{(calcd.)}$ and the difference between these values are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 4—SUBSTITUENT CONSTANTS FOR MULTIPLE SUBSTITUENTS

Substituent	$\Sigma\sigma_{(calcd.)}$	$\Sigma\sigma_{(obs.)}$	$\Sigma\sigma_{(obs.)} - \Sigma\sigma_{(calcd.)}$
4-Methoxy-8-methyl	-0.84	-0.325	+0.016
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy	0.07	0.085	-0.085
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	0.10	0.004	-0.096
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	0.12	0.015	-0.105
3-Iodo-4-methoxy	0.08	0.043	-0.037
3-Nitro-4-methoxy	0.44	0.436	-0.004

The negative sign excepting for methyl substituent indicates that the electron release is greater than expected in these compounds.

Oxidation of methoxyacetophenones: With a view to finding out the behaviour of the acetyl function towards oxidation in the presence of two OCH_3 groups, the oxidation kinetics of 2,6-dimethoxyacetophenone, 2,5-dimethoxyacetophenone and also that of 2-methoxyacetophenone were studied and the data are furnished in Table 5. 2-Methoxy-

TABLE 5—REACTION RATES FOR OXIDATION OF SOME METHOXYACETOPHENONES BY ALKALINE HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS METHANOL

Substrate	$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1})$		
	20°	30°	40°
Acetophenone	2.97	5.59	11.7
2-Methoxyacetophenone	—	2.35	5.20
4-Methoxyacetophenone	1.83	3.09	6.21
2,6-Dimethoxyacetophenone	0.69	1.76	3.02

acetophenone is oxidised at a slower rate ($k_2 = 2.35 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 30°) than 4-methoxyacetophenone. This shows that there is more conjugation between the OCH_3 group and $COCH_3$ group when they are present in the 1,2-positions rather than in the 1,4-positions. When the OCH_3 group is in the *ortho*-position it exercises a greater electron-releasing mesomeric ($-M$) effect. This is responsible for the large decrease in the rate of the reaction. Probably the presence of the acetyl group in the *ortho*-position restricts the rotation of the OCH_3 group with the benzene ring and makes it to lie co-planar with the ring (I). In this position, the OCH_3 group can readily conjugate with the ring and thereby exercises its $-M$ effect to a greater extent. When the OCH_3 group is present in the 4-position, it can exercise its $-M$ effect only to a lesser extent since free rotation is possible. In the case of 2,6-dimethoxyacetophenone, the reaction rate ($k_2 = 1.76 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ at 30°) decreases to 30% of that of acetophenone. Normally, when the OCH_3 function is flanked by two *ortho*-substituents steric inhibition of resonance should operate. But in this compound as the OCH_3 groups are capable of free rotation along the oxygen—benzene

ring axis, they are twisted away from the acetyl

group in order to avoid any steric interaction. In correlating the E_a values of $MeOCH_3$ and $MeSCH_3$ groups, Charton²⁰ assumes that OMe and SMe groups orient in such a way as to minimise their size and so the van der Waals radii for oxygen and sulphur, respectively, are used for these groups. In configuration (II), the two *ortho*-methoxy groups become more planar with the ring which results in a greater electron-release into the aromatic π -electron system with a further decrease in the rate compared with 2-methoxyacetophenone. But the observed value ($1.76 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$) was found to be higher than the calculated value ($0.988 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$). In the structure (II), perhaps the second OCH_3 group may prevent the acetyl group from attaining planarity with benzene ring due to steric interaction of acetyl methyl group with 6- OCH_3 group. This may decrease the conjugation of the acetyl group resulting in an increase of rate constant compared to the rate constant expected on the basis of SER. However, the acetyl group is not subjected to the conventional SIR by the two *o,o'*-substituents, in which case the rate of oxidation will be much faster than that of acetophenone because of the cumulative effect of decreased conjugation of acetyl function and rate-increasing inductive effect of the two OCH_3 groups. The oxidation kinetics of the compound 2,5-dimethoxyacetophenone could not be run due to the formation of some products which interfered with the normal course of the reaction.

Arrhenius parameters: The various Arrhenius thermodynamic parameters for the oxidation of mono-, di- and tri-substituted-acetophenones by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) at 20, 30 and 40° have been evaluated from the specific reaction rates. The values are presented in Table 6. The plots of log rate constant against $1/T$ are linear. For all the above cited reactions the change of entropy varied from -20 to -50 e.u., showing that a complex is formed between the substrate and the oxidant.

In the energy data for the oxidation of mono-substituted-acetophenones and di-substituted-acetophenones it is found that if the entropy factor is assumed to be constant, the change in the energy of activation produced by a substituent or substituents may be calculated from the equation²⁰,

$$E = -2.303 RT \log k_s/k_u$$

where, k_s and k_u are the velocity constants of substituted and unsubstituted acetophenones, respec-

TABLE 6—VELOCITY CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR OXIDATION OF DI- AND TRI-SUBSTITUTED-ACETOPHENONES

Substituents	k_2^* ($\times 10 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$)	$E_{\text{(obs.)}}$ cals	$E_{\text{(calcd.)}}$ cal	$E_{\text{(obs.)}} - E_{\text{(calcd.)}}$ cal
3-Methyl-4-methoxy	1.89	+650	+550	100
3-Methyl-4-ethoxy	2.08	+600	+330	270
3-Fluoro-4-methoxy	6.28	-70	-180	60
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	5.66	-10	-200	190
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	5.88	-30	-210	180
4-Iodo-4-methoxy	6.46	-90	-460	370
4-Methoxy-3,5-dimethyl	3.88	+810	+740	-450
4-Ethoxy-3,5-dimethyl	3.88	+220	+520	-300
3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy	29.3	-1000	-760	-240
3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxy	31.1	-1030	-790	-240
3,5-Diiodo-4-methoxy	29.9	-1010	-1280	+270

* At 80°.

tively. If the substituent effects are additive, the observed increment in activation energy due to two substituents will be the sum of increments due to each substituent alone, i.e.

$$\Delta E_{XY} = \Delta E_X + \Delta E_Y$$

The difference of ≤ 100 cal between $\Delta E_{\text{(obs.)}}$ and $\Delta E_{\text{(calcd.)}}$ is considered to be well within the probable deviation which could occur without infringement of the additivity relationship. This additivity relationship exists in the case of acetophenones where the possibility of group interaction is minimum. On the other hand, in the case of 3-substituted-4-alkoxyacetophenones, the average difference is in the order of 200 cal indicating that the additivity relationship is not applicable here. The data given in Table 6 indicate that 3-substituted-4-alkoxyacetophenones violate seriously the additivity rule of group effects. This shows that the appreciable deviation from the additivity rule in the case of 3-substituted-4-alkoxyacetophenones excepting the fluoro compound, is presumably due to the enhanced conjugative interaction of the 4-alkoxyl groups with the acetyl group. If the enhanced resonance of the alkoxyl and acetyl groups is caused by the 3-substituent, it is clearly a case of steric enhancement of resonance.

The analysis of the kinetic data by different methods lends valuable support for the concept of steric enhancement of resonance.

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